

Contrasting a Conventional Approach with Digital Approach for Brand Communication Scrutiny

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Abstract— Even though businesses now have access to a lot of information, having this information is not enough to make more profitable judgements; instead, careful data analysis is required. Social network services (SNS) are now significant providers of data. SNS are now widely used in many different studies on social science trends as a result of their quick expansion. In this essay, we seek to advance knowledge of social data's potential applications for brand communication research using conventional as well as digital methodologies. The conventional approach is Periodic Evaluation of the Image (PEI). The Sentimental analysis is the digital methodology, which is a Machine Learning techniques that uses a Python programme to analyse large amounts of scientific data. Both approaches are used to analyse the data, and the outcomes are then contrasted. The sample size, industry under study, and extent of the evaluated literature are the paper's limitation.

Keywords— Big Data Analytics, Machine Learning, Sentiment Analysis, Twitter, MonkeyLearn API libraries, Social Network Services(SNS)

I. INTRODUCTION

The amount of information on businesses that is available on the Internet has increased significantly during the last few years. Social Network Services (SNS), a significant source of these data [1], are now frequently utilised in the new social science research trends [2]. Similarly, technology has been crucial to the growth of our civilization as it promotes human wellbeing and works to protect the ecosystem [2]. Additionally, a discussion of democratisation of access to data is done as a result of the expansion of Internet access globally [3].

There were 5.18 billion Internet users worldwide as of April 2023 [2]. In Europe, more than 84% people use the Internet for various things. Although mobile phones were used as the primary method of access, the other devices included laptops, desktops, and tablets [4]. Sale of smartphones are currently the highest globally, and they are shortly anticipated to surpass the sale of personal computers (PCs) [3].

More than 90% of people worldwide have access to a mobile phone, and their usage rate is increasing rapidly. Only 10% of people don't use mobile devices in 2023. The ability to use cell phones, which are now being used to execute tasks were accessible only on PCs and laptops, is changing how people interact in the modern world [4], [5]. Today's smartphones and tablets are used for a variety of purposes, such as making purchases via the internet, accessing financial resources, reading articles and data.

Advertising studies need to take these changes into consideration [5]. Companies generally utilise both conventional and electronic media to communicate with customers. But as for the expansion of consumer communication and the development of brand identity, modern technologies bring up new vistas for businesses. Enhancing our grasp of the interaction between conventional and digital media and how the two affect customer views is crucial in this setting.

To do this, techniques like big data analytics-based approaches must be used. The purpose of big data analytics is to Identifying connections, structures, knowledge or consumer preferences to enhance commercial decision-making[6]. Analysing massive amounts of data that have been either structured or unstructured is known as big data analytics. For this analysis and be able to make decisions on data, firstly the database has to be searched, data mining tools are to be used to organise and then go on to its analysis.

The sources tend to be varied, which makes it difficult to get and later analyse the data, thus this three-step method must overcome a number of obstacles, especially in the early phase of obtaining the data [7].

Notably, it must be explored whether the same conclusions concerning a company's reputation image can be produced using alternative approaches given the current interplay between the virtual channel and the conventional channel [8]. Henceforth, the goal of this research is to increase knowledge of the opportunities that social data presents for brand communication analysis.

By leveraging the Twitter API, a substantial dataset of 1,050,000 tweets from everyday users has been compiled. This dataset serves as a valuable resource for sentiment analysis, aimed at detecting positive or negative sentiments expressed in the tweets. The results of this analysis can be utilized to classify future tweets accurately, offering significant insights into public opinion. This approach is particularly beneficial for brand communication, as it enables businesses to gauge customer sentiment towards their products or services. By understanding public perception, companies can make informed decisions to enhance product quality, develop effective marketing strategies, and innovate new products that align with customer preferences. Overall, sentiment analysis of social media data is a powerful tool for improving customer engagement and driving business growth.

The rest of this paper is organised in a following way. Section II reviews pertinent academic research. Description about the two approaches employed in the current investigation is specified in Section III. The results are then analysed in Section IV with special attention paid to the level of concordance between the two approaches. In Section V, the findings and degree of consistency between the two methodologies are discussed. In Section VI, conclusions are reached.

II. RELATED WORK

When choosing a brand, service or product, public perception is a crucial consideration. Consumers consider the qualities of various goods, services or brands while making decisions. The modern media landscape is evolving, resulting in a confluence of interpersonal contacts, both digital and offline communication. Blanco-Calleja [9] asserts that brands are important assets for businesses because of an ongoing competitive edge [10] that can be managed by the firm itself [11]. Institutions therefore work to build their brands. Sponsorship is one method of this brand promotion [12]. As an example of a powerful brand that has successfully enhanced its image through sponsorship is Banco Santander [13].

Using projective approaches and in-depth interviews, the Periodic Evaluation of the Image (PEI) method was created to help uncover the key elements of a brand's image and the connections among its numerous attributes. [14]. This picture analysis can be conducted for a variety of industries.

Twitter is the most prominent social channel among all online platforms that can be used for evaluating business identities [5], [17]. Hilde A.M. Voorveld [15] outlines future research on brand communication on social media, including a discussion of the theoretic and practical challenges of brand communication in social platforms and a survey regarding the demands of the advertising and media industries business.

Given that brand image is formed through multiple pathways, it would seem important to examine it using various approaches. This is precisely what Shahzad et al. [20] performed in their investigation into the elements that affect consumers' purchasing decisions based on brand perception both online and offline.

The constancy of brands and the projection of project brand image through online as well as conventional settings have been the subject of various studies at the same time [21]– [23]. Table 1 presents an overview of prior studies on brand, organised by method (the conventional vs. digital).

TABLE I
PREVIOUS RESEARCH OF BRAND IMAGE

Authors	Standard Brand Image	Digital Brand Image
Shahzad et al. [19]	No	Yes
Mattar et al.[18]	No	Yes
Jang and Lee[7]	No	Yes
Blanco-Callejo [19]	Yes	No
Cervino [12]	Yes	No
Kuster et al. [13]	Yes	No
Kwon et al. [21]	Yes	Yes

III.METHODOLOGY

PEI METHOD

The PEI is a study technique with a variety of marketing-related applications. The PEI is primarily used to assess a company's or brand's reputation. Data collection is the first phase in the PEI approach. Perspectives that may be defined and thus expressed statistically are what are gathered. Each interviewee is offered a collection of "stimuli" (such as brands, products or entities) before they're interviewed in order to project their opinions. Every prompt can be seen by a card bearing the participant's surname.

To ensure that all three-in-three combinations that can be made with the stimuli have been displayed before the end of the interview, the three-in-three stimuli are shown in the second stage. Eq. (1) defines the total number of possible combinations that can be made with three-in-three inputs.

$$nCq = \frac{n!}{q!(n-q)!} \quad (1)$$

where,

q = Quantity in which n objects combine

n = number of different elements

The interviewees should be given a range of five to seven stimuli for this method of study to work and for the responses to be reliable [23]. The gathered data sample would be too small if there were a maximum of five stimuli used. The strategy is ineffective when a maximum of seven stimuli are shown, and each interview would need a significant amount of time.

The recruiters are thus given triplets of stimuli to sort two of these cards based on how closely they resemble a crucial characteristic (that is absent from the other stimulus) in order to perform the PEI approach. The attributes recorded by the interviewers are then gathered and classified according to their significance by proximity, resulting in as much of the list of attributes as feasible. The qualities are assessed according to their valence or whether it is favourable or unfavourable.

SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The method of measuring and identifying feelings associated with a particular event is called sentiment analysis, aiming to identify and classify the emotions represented in a sample by separating them into favourable, adverse and neutral attitudes. With a Python-developed method, a sentiment analysis in the current study was conducted. The MonkeyLearn API libraries were used to access the algorithm [24]. The application of this approach can be varied, according to Saura et al. [5]. For example, estimates can be

produced using specialised software that combines hybrid models, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. Aside from machine learning, there are other choices, such as algorithm training utilising data mining methods, which increase an algorithm's likelihood of success based on the correctness of its output [27], [28].

Previous studies have demonstrated that sentiment analysis can be used in combination with other Big Data or online information management-based methods for data retrieval. The technique for the current experiment was designed based on studies by Simoes et al. [18], Palomino et al. [25], Ekenga et al. [26] and Reyes-Menendez et al. [27].

The gathered data were filtered and sanitised before sentiment analysis using the following standards:

- Retweets have been cleared off
- URLs were eliminated.
- The tweets that were chosen have to be at least 80 characters long (without the hashtag).
- The tweets were edited to remove any mention of the business
- Spaces were used in place of special characters like "", "=", or "!"

First, two sets of tweets are created: training data and testing data. The dataset that the model would be trained on makes up the training data, and the dataset that the model would be evaluated against makes up the testing data. The dataset is then exposed to three interfaces that work well together:

1. fit () –Interface for Model construction and fitting.
2. predict() - Interface for Facilitates prediction making.
3. transform() - Interface for Converts data.

Models created for sentiment analysis problem:

- BernoulliNB - Bernoulli Naive Bayes
- LinearSVC - Linear Support Vector Classification
- LR - Logistic Regression

Using all the above three models, the accuracy and the probability of the true and false value is displayed. The positive and negative tweets according to the particular model can also be predicted. The sentiment of the data can be predicted by the model. "Accuracy" refers to the probability of an algorithm working well when combined with a machine learning technique for social science big data analytics.

Additionally, the Confusion Matrix is plotted to provide insight into the model's performance across the two categorization types. The Confusion Matrix takes into account both the real ground truth, or gold standard, and the classifier outcome notions. In a binary problem, four alternative solutions exist:

- True negatives (TN)
- True positives (TP)
- False negatives (FN)
- False positives (FP)

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TN} + \text{TP}}{\text{TN} + \text{TP} + \text{FN} + \text{FP}} \quad (2)$$

BERNOULLI NAÏVE BAYES (BERNOULLINB) MODEL

A discrete probability distribution known as the Bernoulli distribution is used to express the discrete probabilities of a random variable that has just one potential value, such as true or false, yes or no, or 1 and 0. Random variables have a p-chances of taking values of 1 and 1-p chances of taking values of 0.

Accuracy of the predicted and testing result: 0.8008125

Fig. 1 Confusion Matrix Plotted using BernoulliNB Model

LINEAR SUPPORT VECTOR CLASSIFICATION MODEL

The extreme points and vectors that aid in the creation of the hyper plane are selected using the Support Vector Machine (SVM). The algorithm is referred regarded as a Support Vector Machine since these extreme situations are known as support vectors. When a dataset is able to be divided into two groups with the use of a single straight line, it is considered linearly separable data, and the classifier used to classify it is known as a linear SVM classifier.

Accuracy of the predicted and testing result: 0.81441875

FIG. 2 CONFUSION MATRIX PLOTTED USING LINEAR SVM MODEL

LOGISTIC REGRESSION (LR) MODEL

With logistic regression, the result of a categorical dependent variable is predicted. As a result, a discrete or category value must be the result. Instead of providing the precise values, which are 0 and 1, it provides the probabilistic values, which fall in the range of 0 to 1. It can be either Yes or No, 0 or 1, true or False, etc. In logistic regression, two maximum values are predicted by fitting a "S" shaped logistic function, as opposed to fitting a regression line (0 or 1).

FIG. 3 CONFUSION MATRIX PLOTTED USING LOGISTIC REGRESSION MODEL

From Figure 1, 2, 3 we observe that the accuracy of BernoulliNB model is 0.80, accuracy of Linear SVM is 0.81 and accuracy of Logistic Regression is 0.82.

Of all the models that have been tried, the Logistic Regression Model works the best. Its accuracy in identifying a tweet's sentiment is almost 82%. It should be mentioned, nonetheless, that the BernoulliNB Model can be trained and predicted upon the quickest. It also obtains 80% classification accuracy.

Additionally, sentiment analysis is less useful when analysing information that uses metaphor, irony, or sarcasm. However, affirmation that the application of this methodology is wholly acceptable in light of the work of Palomino et al. [25], Reyes-Menendez et al. [27] and Bennett et al. [29].

FIG. 4 COMPARISON OF ACCURACY OF BERNOULLINB MODEL, LINEAR SVC MODEL AND LOGISTIC MODEL

IV. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

In the beginning, the data were collected using the PEI approach. Subsequently, additional data examination was carried out utilizing the broad elements of the image, which included the various attributes that the interviewees had noted for every stimulus or financial firm. The characteristics that are most prominent in the interviewee's minds are those with a high probability of occurrence. The level of association is higher according to the PEI technique when more respondents associate any pair of traits more frequently and vice versa.

The interviewee's impression of each stimulus is reflected in the relative image of the stimuli. If every stimulus is considered to be the same, then its value will be equal to the ratio obtained by dividing the total amount of stimuli under consideration by 100. A stimulus is said to have an attribute that is more than the mean if its value is higher than this value. In our situation, for example, a characteristic that appears more often and which correlates is viewed for each entity. According to results, it can be inferred that, evaluating every characteristic with regard to the potential worth of the image, taking into consideration is beneficial.

The stimuli that obtain less assessment are assigned a value of zero, and the stimuli that receive a greater assessment are assigned a value of one hundred. The other stimuli are assigned a value between the two that determines proportionately to the score, culminating in the upright positioning of each. Without taking into account the other brands, each stimulus's own image depicts the interviewees' impression of that stimulus.

It should be highlighted that each entity's unique image contains a considerable amount of perception of the general attributes for the entities under analysis, which is pertinent to the graphics of each entity's unique image. Last but not least, the overall position of the stimuli depicts where each stimulus stands when compared to the others in regard to the set of qualities accomplishing the above setting, however, most follow the same format.

V. RESULT OF SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS

Social information produced by users can be challenging to collect at times. In the current work, we downloaded and analysed tweets using a machine learning-based mechanism to acquire information. The procedure has three steps, as was already described. The business name of the firms' profiles that were the subject of the research was examined first, and any user feedback, opinions, or tweets mentioning those businesses were then obtained using the public Twitter API [30], [31].

One prevalent issue is the accuracy of the data that has been analysed. As a result, it is essential to incorporate processes for identifying errors in the processed data [5]. To increase the accuracy of the algorithm that is being used, first train the data-mining techniques and divide the sample into positive and negative categories based on user comments regarding the companies' industry sentiments.

Based on the webpage that the developer has viewed, the application's name, description, and contact details are complete [5]. After this strategy was created, a token linked to the newly created application's key was produced. Interactions between users and comments posted were included in the total amount of tweets analysed. User generated content (UGC) is described by Saura et al. [5] as the collective expression of users' opinions on digital platforms and in online contexts. The previous ten years, UGC has frequently been utilised to identify the crucial elements for any given topic [5], [24], [36]. Additionally, Figure 5 displays the quantity of tweets detected in accordance with each sentiment (t).

FIG. 5 DATA EXTRACTION PROCESS

After selecting the text that was solely linked to the research issue, including any humorous or sarcastic comments, algorithm training was carried out [17]. The sample and training materials were continually purged of any information.

The most used statistic for evaluating a sentiment analysis algorithm's accuracy is Krippendorff's alpha (α). To evaluate how well observers, coders, judges, or measurement instruments agreed on how to discern between typically unstructured occurrences or give them numerical values, the reliability coefficient known as Krippendorff's alpha (α) was developed. This ought to be 0.667 or higher.

Researchers in the social sciences rely on the data with reliabilities 0.800 because they are unaware of the dangers of drawing incorrect conclusions from unreliable data. In addition, the data with $0.800 > 0.667$ are only taken into consideration when drawing speculative conclusions.

TABLE 2
RELIABILITY OF CONCLUSIONS AND VALUE OF KRIPPENDORFF'S ALPHA

Reliability of Conclusions	Value of Krippendorff's alpha (α)
High	$\alpha \geq 0.800$
Tentative	$\alpha \geq 0.667$
Low	$\alpha < 0.667$

The second phase was applying the sentiment analysis algorithm, which categorises each tweet as having a negative or positive emotion.

VI. DISCUSSION

In the current study, the primary focus was the coherence and synergy of two different research approaches and their findings. Techniques used included sentiment analysis and the PEI approach. It was interesting to see that one of our results using the PEI approach was the emphasis that participants placed on security and confidence. Similar to the situation described above, these outcomes are closely related to the corporate identity and reputation management practises upheld by institutions in the online world.

More generally, our findings show that it is possible to quantify user sentiments towards brand representations of companies using data from social networking site (SNS) like Twitter [16], [35]. In the new digital paradigm, Twitter has just evolved as a SNS where users express their thoughts and leave comments on specific topics that are linked by #Hashtags. In the current work this new 21st-century bidirectional digital communication paradigm may be effectively used for the examination of companies' reputations [5], [32], and [33].

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Numerous social data are produced by the expanding number of social networks and Internet-connected devices. The analysis of these social data by businesses presents many difficulties. With the advent of new technology and digital communication activities, there is a need to raise awareness of the benefits that social data offers for brand communication analysis.

The present research has compared two analysis techniques in this context: sentiment analysis and the PEI methodology. In contrast to conventional interviewing, where the analysis process is slower and subjectivity is introduced by the researcher's actions, sentiment analysis employs machine learning-based mechanisms to collect and analyse Tweets [36]. This allows for a clearer and faster understanding of the data.

The further studies can be made such that it enhances the user interactions and empathetic responses from conversational AI. It can also be intergrated with Customer Relationship Management to better understand customer feedback and improve customer satisfaction. With regards to specific contexts, it can be used to analyse a patient in healthcare industry to improve the medications, treatments and healthcare facilities. In finance industry, Sentimental analysis can be done on financial markets by analysing news, earning reports which would be really beneficial for the traders who invest in stocks. Sentimental analysis helps to mitigate biases and ensures ethical implications.

We can analyse the data more quickly using the Big Data analytics approach that makes use of machine learning techniques than we can with the traditional way. Significant philosophical implications stem from the findings. First, opinions expressed on social media sites like Twitter can aid in a better understanding. Secondly, the sentiment analysis approach employed in this study can be beneficially extended to the examination of significant amounts of data collected from diverse sources. Thirdly, the current study used an innovative methodology to hunt for patterns and markers that had never been examined before [5, 36].

Lastly, findings offer specialists useful, applicable knowledge. The research study's conclusions can be used by those organizations' executives to improve their social image by gaining insight into how users of social media platforms perceive their companies.

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